

Presence and Antimicrobial Resistance of *Escherichia Coli* Isolated from Pork at Slaughterhouses in Selected Provinces of the Mekong Delta, Vietnam

Ngo Van Thong^{1*}, Bui Thi Le Minh², Nguyen Khanh Thuan², Tran Thi Huu Hanh³

¹Faculty of Agriculture and Rural Development, Kien Giang University, ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-7369-2357>

²College of Agriculture, Can Tho University

³Kien Giang Vocational College

ARTICLE INFO

Published Online:
09 January 2026

Corresponding Author:
Ngo Van Thong

ABSTRACT

This study was conducted from August 2023 to August 2024 to evaluate the prevalence, antimicrobial resistance patterns, and distribution of resistance genes in *Escherichia coli* isolated from pork carcasses at slaughterhouses. A total of 96 pork carcass samples were collected from 16 slaughterhouses located in four provinces of the Mekong Delta, including Hau Giang, Kien Giang, Tra Vinh, and Ben Tre. The overall prevalence of *E. coli* was 30.21%. Antimicrobial susceptibility testing revealed high resistance rates to sulfamethoxazole/trimethoprim (81.43%), amoxicillin (57.14%), and ampicillin (48.57%). In contrast, resistance rates to amikacin, amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, cefaclor, cefuroxime, enrofloxacin, and ofloxacin were all below 10%. Multidrug resistance was observed in 80% of the isolates, with the most common resistance patterns involving resistance to three (22.86%) or four (21.43%) antibiotics. Notably, 4.29% of the isolates exhibited resistance to seven or eight antibiotics.

PCR analysis revealed the presence of several antimicrobial resistance genes, including *blaampC* (42.86%), *blaTEM* (21.43%), *blaCTX-M* (4.29%), *tetA* (37.14%), *qnrA* (31.43%), *sullI* (30.00%), *strA* (27.14%), and *catI* (4.29%).

KEYWORDS: *Escherichia coli*, pork, slaughterhouse, Mekong Delta.

INTRODUCTION

Pork is a major source of animal protein in the Vietnamese diet, particularly in the Mekong Delta region, where pig production is highly developed. However, inadequate hygiene during slaughtering and meat handling may result in bacterial contamination, especially by *Escherichia coli*, a common enteric pathogen with a high capacity for antimicrobial resistance. Recent studies have reported alarming levels of antimicrobial resistance in *E. coli* associated with livestock production systems.

Specifically, Duy et al. (2021) reported that 81.1% of *E. coli* isolates from pigs were multidrug-resistant, with nearly 100% carrying resistance genes such as *blaTEM*, *tetA*, and *strA*. In the Mekong Delta, Thong et al. (2022) documented resistance rates of 83.5% to amoxicillin and 78.5% to ampicillin. Meanwhile, Nguyen et al. (2021) detected colistin-resistant *E. coli* in 66% of pork samples collected from traditional markets, raising serious concerns due to the critical role of colistin in treating multidrug-resistant infections. Hien et al. (2023) further reported a high prevalence of *E. coli* contamination in pork carcasses (50%) at slaughterhouses.

Despite these warnings, detailed information on the prevalence and antimicrobial resistance characteristics of *E. coli* at slaughterhouses in the Mekong Delta remains limited. Therefore, this study aimed to determine the occurrence and antimicrobial resistance profiles of *E. coli* isolated from pork carcasses at selected slaughterhouses in the region, thereby providing scientific evidence for food safety monitoring and antimicrobial resistance control in pork production.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Study subjects

The study was conducted on 96 pork carcass samples collected from 16 slaughterhouses located in Hau Giang, Kien Giang, Tra Vinh, and Ben Tre provinces.

2.2. Sample collection and bacterial isolation

Pork carcass samples were collected in accordance with the Vietnamese National Technical Regulation QCVN 01-04:2009/BNNPTNT on sampling and preservation of fresh meat for microbiological examination. Isolation and identification of *E. coli* were performed following the

“Presence and Antimicrobial Resistance of *Escherichia Coli* Isolated from Pork at Slaughterhouses in Selected Provinces of the Mekong Delta, Vietnam”

methods described by Barrow and Feltham (2003) and the Vietnamese standard TCVN 8400-16:2011.

2.3. Antimicrobial susceptibility testing

All *E. coli* isolates were tested for susceptibility to 15 antimicrobial agents using the disk diffusion method on Mueller–Hinton agar (MHA; Merck, Germany), following the guidelines of Bauer et al. (1966). Results were interpreted according to the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI, 2021). The tested antibiotics included amoxicillin, amoxicillin–clavulanic acid, cefuroxime, cefaclor,

gentamicin, streptomycin, kanamycin, amikacin, enrofloxacin, florfenicol, ampicillin, trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole, colistin, ofloxacin, and doxycycline.

2.4. Detection of antimicrobial resistance genes

Antimicrobial resistance genes were detected using polymerase chain reaction (PCR). The nucleotide sequences of primers used for amplification of resistance genes are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Primer pairs were designed based on the nucleotide sequences of antibiotic resistance genes

Antibiotic group	gene	Primer nucleotide sequence (5'-3')	Molecular size (bp)	References
Beta-lactam	<i>blaTEM-F</i>	ATTCTTGAAGACGAAAGGGC	1.150	Jouini <i>et al.</i> (2007)
	<i>blaTEM-R</i>	ACGCTCAGTGGAACGAAAAC		
	<i>blaampC-F</i>	AATGGGTTTTCTACGGTCTG	191	Caroff <i>et al.</i> (1999)
	<i>blaampC-R</i>	GGGCAGCAAATGTGGAGCAA		
	<i>blaCTX-M F</i>	TTAGGAARTGTGGCTGAA		
Tetracyclin	<i>blaCTX-M R</i>	CGATATCGTTGGTGGTTAT	688	Dallenne <i>et al.</i> (2010)
	<i>tetA-F</i>	GGTTCACCTCGAACGACGTCA	577	Kurnia <i>et al.</i> (2018)
<i>tetA-R</i>	CTGTGACAAGTTGCATGA			
Quinolone	<i>qnrA-F</i>	AGAGGATTTCTCACGCCAGG	580	Cattoir <i>et al.</i> (2007)
	<i>qnrA-R</i>	TGCCAGGCACAGATCTTGAC		
Sulfamid	<i>sulII-F</i>	CGGCATCGTCAACATAACC	722	Gow <i>et al.</i> (2008)
	<i>sulII-R</i>	GTGTGCGGATGAAGTCAG		
Phenicol	<i>catI-F</i>	AGTTGCTCAATGTATATAACC	547	Santos <i>et al.</i> (2014)
	<i>catI-R</i>	TTGTAATTCATTAAGCATTCTGCC		
Aminoglycosid	<i>strA-F</i>	CCTGGTGATAACGGCAATTC	546	Merkeviciene <i>et al.</i> (2022)
	<i>strA-R</i>	CCAATCGCAGATAGAAGGC		

2.5. Data analysis

Raw data were processed using Microsoft Excel 2010. The Chi-square test in Minitab version 16 was applied to compare the prevalence of *E. coli* and antimicrobial resistance genes, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Prevalence of *Escherichia coli* in pork carcasses

The prevalence of *E. coli* in 96 pork carcass samples collected from slaughterhouses in the Mekong Delta is presented in Table 2. Significant differences ($p < 0.01$) were observed among provinces. Hau Giang exhibited the highest prevalence (66.66%), followed by Kien Giang (29.17%), whereas Tra Vinh and Ben Tre showed lower rates (12.50%).

Table 2: Presence of *Escherichia coli* in carcasses

Địa điểm khảo sát	Số mẫu khảo sát (mẫu)	Số mẫu dương tính (mẫu)	Tỷ lệ (%)
Hau Giang	24	16	66,66 ^a
Kien Giang	24	7	29,17 ^b
Tra Vinh	24	3	12,50 ^c
Ben Tre	24	3	12,50 ^c
P			<0,01
Tổng	96	29	30,21

These differences likely reflect variations in hygiene conditions, slaughterhouse infrastructure, and the effectiveness of veterinary supervision among localities. Similar findings were reported by Phong et al. (2019), who

identified inadequate separation of clean and dirty areas and the use of contaminated water as major sources of bacterial contamination.

“Presence and Antimicrobial Resistance of *Escherichia Coli* Isolated from Pork at Slaughterhouses in Selected Provinces of the Mekong Delta, Vietnam”

The presence of *E. coli* on pork carcasses not only indicates suboptimal hygienic conditions but also poses significant public health risks when isolates carry antimicrobial resistance genes. Therefore, routine microbiological surveillance and strict quality control at slaughterhouses are essential to ensure food safety.

3.2. Antimicrobial resistance of *E. coli* isolates

Antimicrobial susceptibility testing (Table 3) showed high resistance rates to sulfamethoxazole/trimethoprim (81.43%), amoxicillin (57.14%), and ampicillin (48.57%). These findings are comparable to or higher than those reported in previous domestic studies, reflecting the widespread and prolonged use of broad-spectrum antibiotics in pig production.

Table 3: Antibiotic resistance of *E. coli* isolate

Antibiotic	Number of susceptible isolates	Percentage	Resistant strains	Percentage
Amikacin	67	95,71	3	4,29
Gentamicin	51	72,86	19	27,14
Kanamycin	54	77,14	16	22,86
Streptomycin	44	62,86	26	37,68
Amoxicillin	30	42,86	40	57,14
Amoxicillin + acid clavulanic	65	92,86	5	7,14
Ampicillin	36	51,43	34	48,57
Cefaclor	65	92,86	5	7,14
Cefuroxime	66	94,29	4	5,71
Enrofloxacin	66	94,29	4	5,71
Ofloxacin	64	91,43	6	8,57
Florfenicol	45	64,29	25	35,71
Colistin	56	80,00	14	20,00
Doxycycline	62	88,57	8	11,43
Sul /trimethoprim	13	18,57	57	81,43

Although colistin has been banned for use in livestock production in Vietnam since 2020, colistin-resistant isolates were still detected, suggesting persistence from earlier usage or incomplete enforcement of control measures. Conversely, low resistance rates were observed for amikacin, amoxicillin–clavulanic acid, second-generation cephalosporins, and fluoroquinolones, indicating that these antibiotics remain largely effective. Nevertheless, careful and rational use is required to prevent the emergence of cross-resistance, particularly for antimicrobials also used in human medicine.

3.3. Multidrug resistance patterns

Among the 70 *E. coli* isolates, 80% exhibited multidrug resistance, defined as resistance to three or more antibiotics. The most common resistance patterns involved resistance to three (22.86%) and four (21.43%) antibiotics. Notably, 4.29% of isolates were resistant to seven or eight antibiotics, indicating the presence of highly resistant strains. These findings underscore the urgent need for stricter antimicrobial stewardship in livestock production.

3.4. Distribution of antimicrobial resistance genes

PCR analysis revealed a high prevalence of antimicrobial resistance genes among the isolates (Table 4).

Table 4: Prevalence of antibiotic resistance genes

Gene	Surveyed strains	Number of positive isolates	Percentage
<i>blaTEM</i>	70	15	21,43
<i>blaampC</i>	70	30	42,86
<i>bla CTX-M</i>	70	3	4,29
<i>tetA</i>	70	26	37,14
<i>qnrA</i>	70	22	31,43
<i>SulII</i>	70	21	30,00
<i>catI</i>	70	3	4,29
<i>StrA</i>	70	19	27,14

“Presence and Antimicrobial Resistance of *Escherichia Coli* Isolated from Pork at Slaughterhouses in Selected Provinces of the Mekong Delta, Vietnam”

The *bla*_{ampC} gene was the most frequently detected (42.86%), followed by *tetA* (37.14%), *qnrA* (31.43%), and *sulII* (30.00%). Although the prevalence of *bla*_{CTX-M} was relatively low (4.29%), its presence remains concerning due to its association with extended-spectrum β -lactamase (ESBL)-producing strains. The detection of *catI*, a gene conferring resistance to a banned antibiotic, suggests persistence or horizontal transfer of resistance genes within the slaughterhouse environment.

CONCLUSION

The study demonstrated that *Escherichia coli* was present in 30.21% of pork carcass samples collected from slaughterhouses in the Mekong Delta. The isolates exhibited high resistance rates to sulfamethoxazole/trimethoprim, amoxicillin, and ampicillin, with a high prevalence of multidrug resistance (80%). Several antibiotics, including amikacin, amoxicillin–clavulanic acid, cefaclor, cefuroxime, enrofloxacin, and ofloxacin, remained effective, with resistance rates below 10%.

PCR analysis confirmed the presence of all eight investigated antimicrobial resistance genes among the isolates. These findings highlight the need for continuous monitoring of antimicrobial resistance and stricter control of antibiotic use in pig production and slaughtering processes.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge the support of the Faculty of Agriculture and Rural Development, Kien Giang University; the College of Agriculture, Can Tho University; and the Sub-Departments of Animal Husbandry and Veterinary Medicine of Hau Giang, Kien Giang, Tra Vinh, and Ben Tre provinces.

REFERENCES

1. Duy, D. T., Trung, N. V., & Hoa, N. T. (2021). Antimicrobial resistance of *Escherichia coli* isolated from pigs in southern Vietnam. *Thai Journal of Veterinary Medicine*, 51(3), 401–409. <https://he01.tci-thaijo.org/index.php/tjvm/article/view/249270>
2. Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (MARD). (2022). *Report on the use of veterinary drugs and antibiotics in livestock production in Vietnam*. Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, Vietnam.
3. Ekici, G., & Dümen, E. (2019). *Escherichia coli* and food safety. In M. S. Erjavec (Ed.), *The universe of Escherichia coli* (pp. 1–17). IntechOpen. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.82375>
4. Gyles, C. L., & Fairbrother, J. M. (2010). *Escherichia coli*. In C. L. Gyles, J. F. Prescott, G. Songer, & C. O. Thoen (Eds.), *Pathogenesis of bacterial infections in animals* (4th ed.). Iowa State University Press, Ames, IA.
5. Hai, L. V., & Linh, T. T. M. (2020). Isolation and investigation of tetracycline resistance genes in *Escherichia coli* isolated from pork at slaughterhouses in Dong Nai province. *Journal of Veterinary Science and Technology*, 6, 42–48. (in Vietnamese)
6. Hang, N. T. T., & Mai, P. T. K. (2019). Investigation of antimicrobial resistance in *Escherichia coli* isolated from diseased pigs in several northern provinces of Vietnam. *Journal of Veterinary Science and Technology*, 59(5), 56–62. (in Vietnamese)
7. Hien, N. T., Pham, T. H., & Tran, V. C. (2023). Occurrence of *Escherichia coli* in slaughterhouses and its implications for food safety in the Mekong Delta. *Veterinary Integrative Sciences*, 21(2), 112–120. <https://he02.tci-thaijo.org/index.php/vis/article/view/268458>
8. Hoang, M. T., & Tran, B. L. (2020). Antimicrobial resistance of *Escherichia coli* in pigs in southern Vietnam. *Journal of Rural Development Research*, 12(2), 98–105. (in Vietnamese)
9. Lan, P. T., Toan, N. V., & Hung, T. D. (2020). Detection of antimicrobial resistance genes in *Escherichia coli* isolated from pork in central Vietnam. *Journal of Agriculture and Rural Development*, 11, 68–75. (in Vietnamese)
10. Liu, Y. Y., Wang, Y., & Walsh, T. R. (2016). Emergence of plasmid-mediated colistin resistance mechanism *mcr-1* in animals and human beings in China: A microbiological and molecular study. *The Lancet Infectious Diseases*, 16(3), 277–284. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099\(15\)00424-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099(15)00424-7)
11. Nguyen, T. T., Nguyen, M. H., Le, H. T., & Vo, B. T. (2021). Colistin-resistant *Escherichia coli* isolated from pork sold at traditional markets in Vietnam. *Microbial Drug Resistance*, 27(3), 359–365. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33681373>
12. Nhu, N. T., Khoa, L. V., & Mai, B. T. (2021). Prevalence of ESBL-encoding genes in *Escherichia coli* isolated from pork in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam. *Journal of Biotechnology*, 19(2), 114–121. (in Vietnamese)
13. Phong, L. H., Chau, V. M., Hieu, N. M., Thi, N. T., Cuc, N. T. K., & Hang, B. T. D. (2019). Prevalence of *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella*, and antibiotic residues in pork and chicken meat in several provinces of the Mekong Delta, Vietnam. *Journal of Veterinary Science and Technology*, 7, 47–54. (in Vietnamese)

“Presence and Antimicrobial Resistance of *Escherichia Coli* Isolated from Pork at Slaughterhouses in Selected Provinces of the Mekong Delta, Vietnam”

14. Thong, N. V., Thuan, N. K., & Minh, B. T. L. (2022). Prevalence and antimicrobial resistance profiles of *Escherichia coli* isolated from slaughterhouses in the Mekong Delta, Vietnam. *Veterinary Integrative Sciences*, 20(1), 45–55. <https://he02.tci-thaijo.org/index.php/vis/article/view/268458>
15. Trieu, T. T. L., Thuan, N. K., Toan, N. V., Kiet, L. T., & Khai, L. T. L. (2022). Contamination and antimicrobial resistance of *Escherichia coli* in pork and the slaughterhouse environment in Chau Thanh district, An Giang province, Vietnam. *Can Tho University Journal of Science*, 58(1), 189–196. <https://doi.org/10.22144/ctu.jvn.2022.021>
16. Xuan, D. T., Vu, P. N., & Tien, N. V. (2020). Prevalence of antimicrobial resistance genes in *Escherichia coli* isolated from pork at slaughterhouses in Can Tho province, Vietnam. *Journal of Preventive Medicine*, 30(4), 55–61. (in Vietnamese)